

MAIN UNITS OF FORMAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation : Formal communication may vary in substance and form, but all formal communication shares the characteristics of being rational, structured, and goal oriented. Formal communication is foundational to the emergence of organizational communication as a discipline and critical to the communication as constitutive of organizations perspective.

Key words: Formal communication , Source, Internet , Information Structure

Well, Communication is a way speak and talk each other. Communication means of sending or receiving information, such as phones lines or computers and the imparting or exchanging of information by speaking , writing , or using some other medium . Again , in our daily life , communication helps us build relationship by allowing us to share our experience , and needs , and helps us connect to other . It is the important of human life because , allowing us to express feelings , pass on information and share thoughts . We all need to communicate .

The English term 'Communication' has been evolved from Latin language. 'Communis and communicare' are two Latin words related to the word communication. Communis is noun word, which means common, communiality or sharing. Similarly, communicare is a verb, which means 'make something common'. Some scholars relate the term communication with an English word community. Community members have something common to each other. communities are {supposed to be} formed with the tie of communication. It is the foundation of community. Hence, where there is no communication, there can't be a community.¹

What is formal communication?

Formal communication is exchanging official information between two or more people within the same organization, by following predefined rules and using official channels of communication.

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It is also classified into two types:

Bottom-up: Communication flow is from subordinate to superior authority.

Top-down: Communication flow is from superior authority to subordinate.

2. Lateral or Horizontal

This type of communication takes place between two employees of the same level but working in different departments.

For example, communication that takes place between the Sales Manager and Human Resource Manager.

3. Diagonal or Crosswise

This type of communication takes place between employees of different departments working at different levels.

For example, communication between Salesman and Manufacturing manager^{iv}

Eight Essential Components of Communication

In order to better understand the communication process, we can break it down into a series of eight essential components:

Source

Message

Channel

Receiver

Feedback

Environment

Context

Interference

Each of these eight components serves an integral function in the overall process.

Let's explore them one by one.^v

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